

Austria Country Profile

Q2/2026

Please note:

Most of the information in this report is also available online at:

<https://forschungsdaten.info/fdm-im-deutschsprachigen-raum/oesterreich>

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Austria Country Profile, Q2/2026

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Context information: This report was prepared within the framework of the EOSC Support Office Austria. It constitutes a deliverable of the former Working Group (WG) "Austria Country Profile". As of 2025, the working group transitioned into a monitoring group. Its objective is the regular monitoring of EOSC-related developments in Austria, including Open Science and FAIR-related policies, projects, and activities, as well as research data (management) and computing infrastructures.

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Please note: The group does not claim that the projects, activities, and infrastructures listed in this report are exhaustive. The report reflects the current status at the time of publication. It is updated regularly and aims to provide the most accurate monitoring possible of EOSC-related developments in Austria.

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1 FAIR and Open Science policies in Austria

1.1. Open Science Policy Austria

In February 2022, the Open Science Policy Austria was adopted during a joint presentation to the Council of Ministers by the BMFWF (formerly BMBWF), BMDW and BMK. Austria thus shows its commitment to the Open Science movement and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Find more information and links to the policy document [here](#).

- [Open Science Policy in Austria](#) (German)
- [Open Science Policy in Austria](#) (English)

1.2 Open Science policies by funding organisations

FWF: The largest national funding agency for basic research, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), is committed to supporting open and FAIR science through its open access policy for publications and research data. Since 2019, the FWF requires a data management plan (DMP) for all approved grant proposals. The FWF has defined a minimum set of questions that comprise the DMP that are to be addressed in the DMP template. The FWF DMP is in line with Science Europe's "Core Requirements for Data Management Plans".

- <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-us/what-we-do/open-science>

WWTF: The WWTF, the Vienna Science and Technology Fund, released an Open Science Policy in March 2022:

- <https://wwtf.at/funding/our-principles/downloads/open-access-and-open-science-policy>

1.3 Research data management policies in Austrian research institutions

13 universities in Austria have policies for research data management in place, encouraging in these policies open science practices and the adoption of the FAIR principles:

- [ISTA](#)
- [Johannes Kepler University Linz](#)
- [Medical University Graz](#)
- [Medical University Innsbruck](#)
- [Medical University Vienna](#)
- [Graz University of Technology](#)
- [TU Wien](#)
- [University of Graz](#)
- [University of Innsbruck](#)
- [University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna](#)
- [University of Vienna](#)
- [WU \(Vienna University of Economics and Business\)](#)
- [University of Salzburg](#)

The Natural History Museum Vienna (NHMW) developed an [Open Science Strategy](#).

1.4 Strategies for research recognition

Strategy towards Plan S: Since 2021, the Open Access Policy of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), which is one of the first members of cOAlition S, is in line with Plan S. The BMFWF supports Plan S (see e.g. Anfragebeantwortung durch den Bundesminister für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung Dr. Heinz Faßmann zu der schriftlichen Anfrage (933/J) der Abgeordneten Dr. Helmut Brandstätter, Kolleginnen und Kollegen an den Bundesminister für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung betreffend Plan S).

Furthermore, a working group in the framework of the Forum of Austrian University Libraries (ubifo) is currently developing guidelines for an institutional implementation of Plan S at the Austrian universities.

Strategies towards CoARA: [CoARA - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#). In July 2022, the agreement on reforming research assessment was published after a Stakeholder Assembly bringing together the 350+ organisations from 40+ countries having expressed interest in being involved in advancing research assessment. The Austrian Science Fund (FWF) and several Austrian research institutions commit to COARA and to working on the advancement of the current scholarly assessment system. See: [Austrian signatories](#)

2 Underlying legal frameworks

- General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR – (in Austria: DSGVO): Regulates the protection of personal data and individuals' rights regarding the processing of their data.
- *Forschungsorganisationsgesetzes* – FOG: Is part of the structural legal framework for conducting data protection-compliant research in Austria. Part of these responsibilities includes handling research data properly, ensuring it supports scientific integrity, transparency, and reproducibility.
- *Urheberrechtsgesetz* – UrhG: Regulates the rights of creators over their intellectual works, including their protection, use, and exploitation.
- Freedom of Information Act (in Austria: *Informationsfreiheitgesetz*): As of 1 October 2025. More information see [here](#) (in German only)
- Digital Services Act (DSA): Passed on June 1, 2023.
 - <https://www.bmj.gv.at/themen/EU-und-Internationales/Digital-Services-Act.html> (in German)
- Data Governance Act: As of 24 September 2023, the European Data Governance Act has been applicable in all European Member States. Goal: Promote the exchange of data, with due regard to GDPR regulation. The Act is part of the [European Data Strategy](#).
- Open Data Directive (formerly Directive on the re-use of public sector information - PSI): The European [Open Data and PSI Directive](#) provides the legal basis for the re-use of public sector data and sets a minimum set of rules. Focus is on non-personal data that are made freely available in the public interest. The Commission Implementing Regulation lays down a list of specific high-value datasets and the arrangements for

their publication and re-use became effective on 9 February 2023 (IR (EU) 2023/138).

More details see [here](#).

- Some technical information for the implementation of the Directive in Austria:
- According to § 11 IWG 2022, open data and also high-value datasets must be linked to the Austrian data portal [data.gv.at](https://www.data.gv.at), unless this requires an unreasonable amount of effort (cf. adding data <https://www.data.gv.at/daten/daten-hinzufuegen/>), and for this purpose the data or datasets must be described in their core elements based on the Austrian standard metadata [data.gv.at](https://go.gv.at/ogdmetade) (cf. <https://go.gv.at/ogdmetade>).
- More detailed information on the provision of open data by the administration can be found in the Open Government Data (OGD) framework (cf. <https://go.gv.at/ogdframede>).

3 ESFRI participation in Austria

ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, supports a coherent and strategy-led approach to policymaking on research infrastructures in Europe. ESFRI selects proposals of RIs in strategic areas of research and with an adequate level of maturity to become ESFRI Projects and identifies successfully implemented RIs to become ESFRI Landmarks.

While ESFRI is the policy and strategy forum, ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortia) represent the legal and operational framework that allows ESFRI-prioritized research infrastructures to operate efficiently across European borders.

Austrian membership in ERICs:

- BBMRI-ERIC: International research infrastructure for biobanks and biomolecular resources, headquartered in Graz. Austria participates through the Medical University of Graz (lead of the entire ERIC).
- CLARIN ERIC/DARIAH ERIC: In Austria CLARIAH-AT: Participation through the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ACDH-ÖAW).
- CESSDA-ERIC: Connects national data archives across Europe and makes datasets (e.g., surveys, population data, political studies) accessible. Participation through AUSSDA.
- ESS-ERIC: European Social Survey. Participation through the Institute for Advanced Studies (IHS).
- SHARE-ERIC: Research infrastructure for social and health research on aging. Participation through Johannes Kepler University Linz.
- ACTRIS-ERIC: Europe-wide network for atmospheric measurements, with participation from several Austrian institutions (<https://www.actris.eu/about/who-we-are/actris-countries>).
- ERINHA-ERIC: Research infrastructure dealing with highly dangerous pathogens. Participation through the Medical University of Graz.
- ILL-ERIC: Research infrastructure for neutron science. Participation through the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW).
- EURO-Bioimaging-ERIC: Research infrastructure for imaging in life sciences and medicine. Participation through the Austrian Bioimaging Node.

- CTAO-ERIC: Research infrastructure for astroparticle physics. Participation through the University of Innsbruck.
- [on the ESFRI Roadmap] EBRAINS: Europe's Digital Infrastructure for Brain Research. Medical University of Innsbruck is an Associate Member.

AUSTRIA

Leader

📍 Landmarks: **BBMRI-ERIC**

Member

📍 Landmarks: **PRACE, ACTRIS, EPOS ERIC, ERINHA, Euro-Biomed Imaging ERIC, CTAO, ILL, CESSDA ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, ESS ERIC, SHARE ERIC**

Observer

▶▶ Projects: **IFMIF-DONES**

📍 Landmarks: **ELIXIR**

Prospective

▶▶ Projects: **DANUBIUS-RI, eLTER RI, EIRENE RI, EHRI, GGP**

CLOSE

ESFRI Research Infrastructures with Austrian participation. Source: ESFRI RI Portfolio Map (29 June 2026). <https://ri-portfolio.esfri.eu/ri-portfolio/map/>

4 Projects supporting RDM, Open Science, FAIR and EOSC

4.1 National projects and calls

Projects co-funded by the BMFWF under the "(Digital) Research Infrastructures" call (co-funded by NextGenerationEU) were completed in June 2026, including:

- ARI&Snet: <https://forschungsdaten.at/arisnet/>. ARISnet is to be taken over by ACOMarket and established as a sustainable infrastructure for Austrian institutions.
- Shared RDM Services and Infrastructure: <https://forschungsdaten.at/sharedrdm/>. The project fostered communities that will continue their regular meetings beyond the project's duration.

The focus of RDM projects in Austria has since shifted from the national level toward two main areas: the European level on the one hand (EOSC), and the institutional level on the other. National collaboration currently takes place primarily through topic-specific working groups, tool communities, and established networks. Developments can still be followed through [Cluster Forschung+Daten](#) which continues its work as an information hub and networking platform.

4.2 EU projects

Active EU projects fostering Open Science, FAIR and the EOSC (involving partners from the Austrian RPOs):

- DISSCo: <https://www.dissco.eu/>. The Distributed System of Scientific Collections is a new world-class Research Infrastructure (RI) for Natural Science Collections. Currently, DISSCo is awaiting approval to be converted into an ERIC. After the transition, the participating institution for Austria will be the Natural History Museum Vienna.
- EOSC-CONNECT (Connecting National Nodes to the EOSC Federation) (duration: 1 September 2026-28 February 2029) aims to expand, consolidate, and further advance the EOSC Federation by focusing on national EOSC Nodes. These nodes, supported, endorsed, or acknowledged by relevant national authorities such as ministries or national funding agencies, play a strategic role in ensuring alignment with national strategies, fostering researcher engagement, and leveraging existing infrastructures and expertise. The project brings together partners from 14 countries (Austria, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland) with the ambition to:
 - Build and connect independently managed, sustainable National Nodes recognized as national entry points to the EOSC Federation
 - Address existing gaps in federating capabilities at technical, legal, and organizational levels to simplify and advance the sharing of data and costly resources across countries and disciplines
 - Support the evolution of the EOSC Federation and increase its adoption by demonstrating its tangible benefits
 - Champion the EOSC Federation within the European research community

The project is led by CSC Finland and EOSC SOA, and the future Austrian EOSC Node is represented by TU Graz, TU Wien, and Open Knowledge Maps. Point of contact: Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (TU Graz)
- EOSC Gravity: <https://eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/eosc-gravity/>. EOSC GRAVITY supports the transition of the European co-programmed Partnership for EOSC into its new governance and funding framework. Through open calls, EOSC GRAVITY provides funding to support the EOSC Federation by encouraging the creation of EOSC Nodes, inter-project collaboration, and will support the revision of SRIA 2.0. The further evolution of the EOSC Federation is being chartered through measures to monitor and report on EOSC Partnership KPIs and to establish a methodology to assess the impact of EOSC. EOSC GRAVITY pulls the EOSC communities of stakeholders together to contribute to a smooth and effective transition from the Partnership to a new governance and funding framework for EOSC post-2027. Point of contact: Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (TU Graz)

- EuroCC: <https://hpc-portal.eu/>. Goal: to develop in European countries National Competence Centers (NCC) in High Performance Computing (HPC), Big Data and Artificial Intelligence. This NCC will be the contact point for academia, industry and public organisations for collaborations in HPC, Big Data and AI projects, and the NCC will document, map and coordinate activities i. Current phase runs until 30 March. From 1 April 2026 to 31 March 2029 it will be run as EuroCC III, classic high-performance computing. Point of contact (POC): Markus Stöhr/BOKU
- OSTRails: <https://ostrails.eu>. Aims to improve the way we plan, track, and assess scientific knowledge. It wants to go beyond current methods, working with different countries and themes to make existing systems better and connect key parts for research and innovation (R&I). The goal is to create a practical, open, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) system for European scientific research. OSTRails involves major players in Data Management Plans, FAIR Assessment Tools, and Scientific Knowledge Graphs to set standards and make data plans more efficient across Europe.

5 Networks supporting RDM, Open Science, FAIR and EOSC

- ABOL – Austrian Barcode of Life - ein Netzwerk für Biodiversität: <https://www.abol.ac.at/>
- CLARIAH-AT: <https://clariah.at/de/>
- Citizen Science Network Austria: <https://www.citizen-science.at/netzwerk> Österreich forscht: [Citizen Science Projekte - Österreich forscht \(citizen-science.at\)](https://www.citizen-science.at/citizen-science-projekte-oesterreich-forscht/)
- Cluster Forschung+Daten: <https://forschung-daten.at/>
- DOI-Service Austria: <https://orcid-austria.org/>
- e-IRG - e-Infrastructure Reflection Group: <https://e-irg.eu/>
- Elixir (Austria is Observer since 2023): <https://elixir-europe.org/> and <https://elixir-europe.org/news/austria-joins>
- European Citizen Science Association (ECSA): <https://www.ecsa.ngo/>
- EOSC Support Office Austria: <https://eosc-austria.at/>
- FIDELIS Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/> (Austria represented through CESSDA, LIBER, OpenAIRE)
- GEO (Group on Earth Observation) – GEO Data Working Group: Review on Data Sharing and Data Management Principles and crosswalk towards FAIR and Trust Principles. https://www.earthobservations.org/data_wg.php
- GO FAIR Austria: <https://www.gofair.foundation/national-offices>
- KEMÖ - Kooperation E-Medien Österreich: [Austrian Academic Library Consortium \(KEMÖ\)](https://www.kemoe.at/)
- Kulturerbe digital: <https://www.kulturerbe-digital.at>
- Kulturpool <https://kulturpool.at/>
- OANA – Open Science Network Austria: <https://www.oana.at> (2012-2021; comment: restructured under the umbrella of uniko and under the title of "Open Science Austria (OSA)")

- OpenAIRE – The National Open Access Desk (NOAD) is led by the University of Vienna. The NOADs are committed to supporting the adoption and implementation of Open Science in their national research environments. They nurture collaborations with national stakeholders and experts and leverage those connections to populate, curate, and update the content of their country pages on a regular basis.
<https://www.openaire.eu/os-austria>
- Open Science Austria - OSA: <https://www.osa-openscienceaustria.at>
- Open Science - Lebenswissenschaften im Dialog: <https://www.openscience.or.at/de>
- ORCID Austria: <https://orcid-austria.org/>
- OSCA (Open Scientific Collections Austria; Portal - OSCA - Open Scientific Collections Austria): <https://osca.science/portal/>
- Plattform Registerforschung: <https://www.registerforschung.at/>
- RDA Austria - <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-austria>

6 RDM and Open Science training

Workshops: Many institutions offer related workshops within their respective training frameworks.

Webinars: At the national level, the webinar series “RDM in Austria” has been running for several years:

- [webinar recordings on YouTube](#)
- [webinar materials from 2020 - 2023](#)
- [webinar materials after 2023](#)

Certificate courses and lectures: current, quality-assured courses in Open Science, Research Data Management (RDM), and Data Stewardship (certificates awarded):

- [Certificate Course Data Steward](#) at the University of Vienna, duration 2 semesters (part-time); scope 15 ECTS credits; language: English; costs: yes
- [Introduction into Research Data Management](#) at the TU Wien: Lecture for bachelor and master students; duration: 1 semester, scope 3 ECTS credits; language: English; costs: no
- [Data Stewardship](#) (part of Data Science curriculum) at the TU Wien: Lecture for master students from the Faculty of Informatics; duration 1 semester; scope: 3 ECTS credits; language: English; costs: no
- [Universitätskurs Data Steward](#) - University course (certificate) at the Karl Franzens University Graz; 2 semesters: 16 ECTS; language: German; costs: yes
- Research Data Management: [Foundations and Practice](#), [Lifecycle and Sharing](#) at the University of Salzburg; two cross-faculty courses for doctoral students; duration: 1 semester each; 3 ECTS each; language: English; cost: no
- [Research Data Quest: Mastering Open Science in Psychology](#) at the University of Salzburg; elective module for master students from the Department of Psychology; duration: 2 semesters; 8 ECTS; language: German and English; cost: no
- Internal training courses for employees at the University of Salzburg: Data Protection in Theory and Practice (English and German), Informationsfreiheitsgesetz (IFG) - Das

- Portal data.gv.at, Datenkuratierung und Veröffentlichung von Forschungsdaten, Research Data Management, Open Access leicht gemacht - Publikation, Finanzierung, Rechtsfragen, AI Law and Governance (English and German); cost: no
- Introduction to Open Science: Research, Access, and Education at TU Graz; elective module for PhD students; duration: 1 semester; 3 ECTS; language: English; costs: no

7 National structure of EOSC

The Austrian EOSC initiative started in 2021 after the foundation and first General Assembly of the EOSC Association. The ACONET Association [note: not to be confused with the National Research and Education Network (ACONet), originally funded by the Austrian Ministry of Science within the framework of the ACONET Association and was established in 1990 under the responsibility of TU Wien. Since 1992 ACONet has been operated by the University of Vienna.] is the signatory of the Memorandum of Understanding with the EOSC Association and thus the Austrian EOSC Mandated Organisation. To carry out the work this entails towards the implementation of EOSC, however, ACONET Association has created a dedicated body, the EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA). ACONET Association's role can therefore be understood as legal representative with no operational plans or executive power over the EOSC-related tasks in Austria. This is done by the EOSC SOA, whose members include Austrian research performing organisations.

EOSC Support Office Austria (EOSC SOA): Founded in 2021, EOSC SOA acts as the coordinator of EOSC activities in the country and as closest link to the EOSC Association. Its operational goals translate those of the EOSC Association into the national context. [EOSC SOA](#) is managed by the Management Board, chaired each year by a member of the organisation on a rotational basis. Since November 2025, Dimitri Prandner (dimitri.prandner@jku.at) from the JKU has been the Board's chair. The [EOSC Austria Annual Activity Report 2024/2025](#) describes the achievements in the last year.

- Website: <https://eosc-austria.at/>

Contacts:

- ACONET Association: vorsitz@aconet.at
- Chair of the EOSC SOA General Assembly: Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi, ilire.hasani-mavriqi@tugraz.at
- EOSC SOA Secretariat: contact@eosc-austria.at
- EOSC Association Steering Board representative: Stefan Hanslik, Head of Unit of Technical Science at the BMFWF, stefan.hanslik@bmbwf.gv.at

8 Current Austrian infrastructure landscape

Austria has several organisations that offer generic and discipline-specific e-infrastructure services. A large number of Austrian research institutions offer institutional publication servers for open access to research publications. In addition, there is a growing number of public institutions providing institutional data repositories. Access to content is generally open and free

of charge at point of use. Use of the systems is subject to the applicable policies and terms of use of each system. There is currently no central access point (central entry point) to Austrian research results. Many of the systems, however, synchronise with data hubs such as DataCite, OpenAIRE, and BASE. The infrastructure landscape is based on distributed systems.

BMFWF provides an aggregating portal for research infrastructures (Forschungsinfrastruktur Datenbank). This public database offers an overview of national research infrastructures and serves as an information platform where users can find and offer infrastructures for new cooperation projects: <https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmfwf.gv.at/en>

QR-Code for BMFWF database: EOOSC RI Cluster

Clusters >

EOOSC AUSTRIA

STATISTICS BY REGION | CLUSTER | MONITORING | ESFRI-AT-MAPPING | GALLERY

CLUSTERS

- Biodiversity & LTER
- DiSSCo AT – Distributed System of Scientific Collections Austria
- EOOSC Austria**
- High Performance Computing - EuroCC Austria
- Quantum Science and Technology in Austria
- Security and disaster research

[Website](#) →

– EOOSC process-relevant infrastructures

The **European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC)** envisages the development of a federated European data infrastructure that integrates cloud solutions and services in the scientific sector and later extends these data and services to the public sector and industry.

The cluster page presents "EOOSC process-relevant infrastructures" from Austria and is continuously expanded with new research infrastructures.

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KONTAKT

EOOSC Kontakt:

Bundesministerium für Frauen, Wissenschaft und Forschung
– Federal Ministry of Women, Science and Research

Abteilung II/3 – Grundlagenforschung (MINT) und Forschungsinfrastrukturen
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<https://eosc-austria.at>
<https://eosc.eu>

Image: Screenshot from Forschungsinfrastruktur website, Clustering for „EOOSC Austria“. Status as of 29.06.2026: Services, https://forschungsinfrastruktur.bmfwf.gv.at/en/cluster/eosc-austria_4

8.1 Data and computing infrastructures

Infrastructures providing domain specific (data) services:

- AUSSDA (The Austrian Social Science Data Archive) <https://aussda.at/en/> is a data infrastructure for the social science community in Austria and offers a variety of research support services, primarily data archiving and help with data re-use. AUSSDA is the national Service Provider within CESSDA ERIC.
 - The new Teaching and Learning Dataverse provides a collection of data that is particularly useful for teaching. Selected by members of AUSSDA's User Advisory Board and educators teaching social science research methods, AUSSDA vouches for the usability of these data in courses. <https://data.aussda.at/dataverse/teaching/>
- The Austrian NeuroCloud (ANC) <https://anc.plus.ac.at/> is a FAIR-enabling infrastructure designed to support sustainable research data management in cognitive neuroscience. The ANC is committed to the long-term preservation, accessibility, and FAIR stewardship of cognitive neuroscience research data. As a domain-specific, open repository, the ANC enables researchers to manage and share data across the entire research lifecycle, from acquisition and curation to publication and reuse. The ANC is hosted at and sustained by the University of Salzburg.
- BBMRI ERIC - <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>. BBMRI-ERIC is a distributed research infrastructure of biobanks and biomolecular resources. For its Member States, it provides expertise and services on a non-economic basis and facilitates access to collections of partner biobanks and biomolecular resources. BBMRI-ERIC is established for an unlimited period of time. The Central Executive Management Office is located in Graz, Austria.
- CLARIN <http://digital-humanities.at/en>. The Austrian Academy of Science is participating in CLARIN (ACDH-OEAW): Digital Humanities Austria (dha) is an open network of institutional partners in Austria joining efforts to realize a new understanding of humanities research in a digital environment. These efforts are an integral part of the Austrian commitment to the research infrastructure consortia CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-EU, pan-European communities of practice organized as networks of centres sharing resources, tools and knowledge.
- CyVerse Austria <https://www.tugraz.at/sites/cyverse/home>. Provides life scientists with powerful computational infrastructure to handle huge datasets and complex analyses, thus enabling data-driven discovery. The extensible platforms provide data storage, bioinformatics tools, image analyses, APIs, and more. CyVerse Austria uses open source code from CyVerse US (University of Arizona).
- EODC. www.eodc.eu Operates a virtualised, distributed earth observation (EO) data centre, providing collaborative IT infrastructure for archiving, processing, and distributing EO data. Together with its multi-national partners from science, the public and private sectors EODC fosters the use of satellite-derived geoinformation. Its focus ranges from scientific research to operational services in the areas of water resources and land monitoring, agricultural applications, and humanitarian aid and civil security. Infrastructures characteristics: Multi-Petabyte-scale storage (discs and tape) connected to the EODC cloud and to EODC.
- Ethnographic Data Archive. <https://eda.univie.ac.at/>. The Ethnographic Data Archive (EDA) offers support for research data management, digitization and long-term

archiving of primarily ethnographic and qualitative data. Ethnographic research places high demands on methodological knowledge, but also on reciprocity, reflexivity and ethics. For these reasons, the archiving and subsequent use of ethnographic data entails major challenges of a pragmatic, ethical and legal nature. The research-supporting Ethnographic Data Archive (EDA) has the task of digitizing data from ethnographic research and making it available through long-term archiving in Phaidra. EDA is a service for members of the University of Vienna. This service is available for current and historical research, as well as for ongoing and completed projects, etc.

- GEOCLIM Long Term Archive: EODC & CCCA-DC implemented a tape-based long-term archive on two locations at TU Wien and VSC
- GeoSphere Austria Data Hub <https://data.hub.geosphere.at/>. Provides high quality datasets for research and public & commercial use. [News:] GeoSphere Austria Data Hub uses the CCCA - migration for the extension to the DataCite schema and aligned DOIs with available data. GeoSphere Austria TETHYS RDR is a research data repository, which specialises in collecting and storing geoscientific research data and making it available to the public. [NEWS:] TETHYS RDR got approval by CORE TRUST SEAL in March 2024.
- Kulturpool <https://kulturpool.at/> was released in 2024 and provides a portal allowing to find digitalisates (2D, 3D, audio, ...) from museums, archives, and libraries for currently >40 institutions. The access to the original is via the webpage of the respective institution. In addition, training material is offered.
- OSCA (Open Scientific Collections Austria). In 2025, OSCA will join the European research infrastructure DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections). DiSSCo connects and digitises natural science collections across Europe, providing open access to scientific knowledge regardless of location. As the largest network of natural history museums, botanical gardens, universities and research institutions in Europe, it promotes innovation and knowledge sharing. In Austria, the OSCA consortium coordinates the digitisation of national collections, making them digitally accessible for research and the public. <https://osca.science/portal/> - Released the first version of the portal for collection data from natural sciences and geological sciences. After funded the first 3 years by the BMKOES it got a prolongation to develop into a research infrastructure from the BMBWF.
- Open Knowledge Maps - A non-profit providing AI-driven visual discovery of research publications. Most recently, the Consortium of Swiss Academic Libraries (CSAL) joined as a member of Open Knowledge Maps. The partnership is further enhanced by the participation of the Swiss Library Service Platform (SLSP), the operator of Switzerland's national library platform, swisscovery, which will bring Open Knowledge Maps visualisations to over 500 libraries. This widespread support from the Swiss research community will strengthen Open Knowledge Maps and its open infrastructure as a part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

8.2PID infrastructures

- DOI-Service Austria: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/library/digital-scholarship/austrian-national-pid-services>
- ORCID Austria: <https://orcid-austria.org/>

8.3 Network infrastructures

- ACOnet – the Austrian NREN (www.ACO.net)
 - high performance network infrastructure (contract and infrastructure renewal finished June 2023)
 - member of GÉANT
 - ACOnet Identity Federation (eduID.at - member of eduGAIN)
- Austrian Quantum Fiber Network (AQUnet)
 - FFG R&D infrastructure funding project coordinated by the ACONET Association
 - intended to complement and enable the (new) ACOnet backbone infrastructure for CLONETS and EuroQCI-related research
- EGI – At the beginning of 2022, ACONET Association joined the EGI Foundation
 - The EGI is a European federation of e-Infrastructures, providing services, data, processing capabilities and knowledge from its partners to the scientific community. Its decentralised federated cloud architecture has been created as an 'Infrastructure as a Service' (IaaS), was built around open standards and is driven by the requirements of a scientific community. Scopes are to facilitate the (joint) access to general/specialised ICT resources for interested users at pan-European scale, to offer related training and thus to promote collaborative science and to increase the effectiveness of existing resources. While the first steps of this upcoming collaboration between EGI and Austrian entities will have to be discussed in 2022, several Austrian partners already participate together with EGI in the H2020 project EGI-ACE (coordinated by the EODC Earth Observation Data Centre, Vienna), developing an EOSC Compute platform and contributing to the implementation of the EOSC Data Commons. In this context, PaaS' will be provided to the EOSC, including data spaces with analytics tools and federated access services.

8.4 HPC infrastructures

- The Austrian e-infrastructure became part of the EuroHPC JU via assembly of an AT HPC Competence Centre and membership to the CINECA Consortium implementing LEONARDO
- MACH-2 – The massively parallel shared memory supercomputer “MACH-2” is operated in the frame of a project by the Johannes Kepler University (JKU) Linz on behalf of a consortium of several Austrian universities and research institutions.
- ASC – Austrian Scientific Computing, formerly known as the Vienna Scientific Cluster (VSC) – is a collaboration of several Austrian universities that provides supercomputer resources and technical support to their users. The current flagship systems, [VSC-4](#) and [VSC-5](#), are the fastest supercomputers in Austria. They power advanced research and innovation in fields such as physics, chemistry, climate science, life sciences, engineering, and beyond.
- [SCC - Salzburg Collaborative Computing](#) is an HPC infrastructure hosted at the University of Salzburg, funded by BMFWF and Land Salzburg. It is set to bridge the gap between providing a flexible and low entry barrier system for the scientific community in Salzburg and participating in federated national HPC endeavors like MUSICA.
- The AI Factory Austria AI:AT supports customers as an independent, trustworthy partner in using AI effectively - through sovereign infrastructure, hands-on expertise,

enablement, embedded in an ecosystem of research, startups and industry (<https://ai-at.eu/>).

8.5 Data repositories/data centers/data portals

At current state, 54 "Austrian" repositories are registered by OpenDOAR (https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/view/repository_by_country/Austria.html) and 51 data repositories by re3data ([https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries\[\]=AUT](https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries[]=AUT)).

Below there is an excerpt of available data repositories and/or data centres in Austria (NB: not all listed on the re3data platform).

Name of repository	Type (repository/ data center/data portal/service)	Link	Comment
Cross-disciplinary/Institutional			
Repository of the International Institute of Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)	Repository	https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data	
Digital Repository KUG-PHAIDRA (University of Music and Performing Arts Graz – KUG)	Repository	https://phaidra.kug.ac.at/	
Institutional Repository of the University of Art and Design Linz	Repository	https://phaidra.ufg.at/	
Institutional Repository of the University of Applied Arts	Repository	https://phaidra.bibliothek.uni-ak.ac.at/	
ISTA Research Explorer	Repository	https://research-explorer.ista.ac.at/	
PHAIDRA @ FH St Pölten	Repository	https://phaidra.fhstp.ac.at/	
mdw Repository	Repository	https://repo.mdw.ac.at	
NHM Forschungsdaten-Repository	Repository	http://datarepository.nhm-wien.ac.at	
NHM Git Account	Repository	https://github.com/nhmvienna	Github
Phaidra - Repository of the University of			

Veterinary Medicine, Vienna	Repository	https://phaidra.vetmeduni.ac.at	
TU Graz Repository	Repository	https://repository.tugraz.at/	
TU Wien Research Data	Repository	https://researchdata.tuwien.at	Core Trust Seal (CTS) - valid until 2028
Universität Innsbruck - Data Repository	Repository	https://researchdata.uibk.ac.at	
University of Vienna PHAIDRA	Repository	https://phaidra.univie.ac.at	
Discipline specific			
ARCHE - A Resource Centre for the Humanities	Repository	https://arche.acdh.oeaw.ac.at	
AUSSDA Dataverse	Repository	https://data.aussda.at/	Core Trust Seal (CTS) - obtained again - valid until 2026
Austrian NeuroCloud	Repository	https://anc.plus.ac.at/	
EODC - Earth Observation Data Centre	Data centre	https://www.eodc.eu/	
Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System (GAMS)	Repository	https://gams.uni-graz.at	Core Trust Seal (CTS) - obtained again - valid until 2027
Geosphere	Repository	https://www.geosphere.at/en/data/data-center/tethys-rdr	Data repository Tethys RDR
	Data portal	https://data.hub.geosphere.at/	Weather, climate, environment and geophysics data. Metadata exchanged with the portal Open Data Austria (data.gv.at)
			Digital objects from museums,

Kulturpool	Data portal/Service / Competency Centre	https://kulturpool.at/	libraries and archives. The access to the original is via the webpage of the respective institution.
Tethys RDR - Geologische Bundesanstalt (GBA), Data Publisher for Geoscience Austria	Repository	https://www.tethys.at/	Core Trust Seal (CTS) – valid until 2027
Topic specific			
Thanados - The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures	Repository	https://thanados.net/	
Public sector information			
Open Data Austria - data.gv.at	Repository	https://www.data.gv.at/	Central Austrian portal for public sector data. Data are provided to European portal data.europa.eu . The basis for data.gv.at is the cooperation agreement between the federal government, cities, provinces and municipalities - with the stipulation to plan, implement, operate and further develop a joint portal.
	Open Government	https://digitales.wien.gv.at/op-en-data/	Data Portal Vienna

	Data Vienna		
	Open Government		
	Data Graz	https://data.graz.gv.at/graz/	Data Portal Graz
Open Data Portal Austria	Data portal	https://www.opendataportal.at	Central platform for open data in the areas of business, culture, NGO/NPO, research and civil society in Austria
Mobilitätsdaten Österreich	Data portal	https://mobilitydata.gv.at/	Mobility data
Geoportal Stadt Wien	Data portal	https://geoportal.wien.gv.at/map/main/geo-daten/	Geodata
INSPIRE Österreich	Data portal	https://www.inspire.gv.at/geoportale/agrartlas-agrarportal.html	Austrian spatial data infrastructure – high value datasets & thematic data
AMDC - Austrian Micro Data Center	Data centre	https://www.statistik.at/services/tools/services/amdc-mikrodaten-fuer-die-wissenschaft	Data only available via Remote Research Environment of Statistik Austria for a limited period of time
Basemap	Data portal	https://basemap.at/	Administrative base map (geodata) of Austria
Österreichischer Kataster	Data portal	https://kataster.bev.gv.at/	Austrian land register
Die Graphenintegrations-Plattform GIP	Service	https://www.gip.gv.at/	Public sector reference system for transport infrastructure data

8.7 Publication/document servers

At current state, 54 "Austrian" repositories are registered by OpenDOAR (https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/view/repository_by_country/Austria.html) and 51 data repositories by re3data ([https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries\[\]=AUT](https://www.re3data.org/search?query=&countries[]=AUT)). NB: Not all existing repositories are registered in a directory.

Name of repository	Link	Comment
Institutional publication/document servers		
ia[repository	https://repository.akbild.ac.at	
BOKU:epub	http://epub.boku.ac.at/	
DOOR	https://door.donau-uni.ac.at/	
Austrian Institute for Health Technology Assessment Repository for Publications	https://eprints.aihta.at/	Former known as LBI HTA
Elektronisches Publikationsportal der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften	https://verlag.oeaw.ac.at/produkte/oe-aw-publikationen/c-116	
ePLUS (Open Access Publikationsserver der Universität Salzburg)	http://eplus.uni-salzburg.at	
ePubWU Institutional Repository (ePubWU)	http://epub.wu.ac.at	
FHpub	https://fhpub.fh-vie.ac.at	
FWF-E-Book-Library	https://e-book.fwf.ac.at/	
IIASA PURE	http://pure.iiasa.ac.at/	
INIS Repository	http://inis.iaea.org/search	
IRIHS - Institutional Repository at IHS	https://irihs.ihs.ac.at	
IST Austria Research Explorer	https://research-explorer.app.ist.ac.at	
Institutional Repository of the Mozarteum University	http://repository.moz.ac.at	
JKU ePub	http://epub.jku.at/	
Kirchlicher DokumentenServer der AKThB und des VkwB (KiDokS)	https://kidoks.bsz-bw.de/home	
MedUni Wien ePub	https://repositorium.meduniwien.ac.at	

Online Publikationsserver der Fachhochschule Vorarlberg	https://opus.fhv.at	
People @ FH Burgenland	https://people.fh-burgenland.at/	
Publication Database of the Vienna University of Technology	https://publik.tuwien.ac.at/start.php?l_ang=2	
Publikationsserver der Universität Klagenfurt (netlibrary)	https://netlibrary.aau.at/	
pub.mdw - Open Access Publication Server	https://pub.mdw.ac.at	
repositUM (TU Wien Open Access Platform)	https://repositum.tuwien.at	
TUGraz OPEN Library	http://openlib.tugraz.at/	
University of Innsbruck Digital Library	http://diglib.uibk.ac.at/	
u:scholar	http://uscholar.univie.ac.at/	
uni≡pub (unipub)	http://unipub.uni-graz.at/	
Phaidra (@University of Vienna)	https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/	
State and county library servers		
Digitale Landesbibliothek Oberösterreich	http://digi.landesbibliothek.at/	Digitale Landesbibliothek Oberösterreich
Discipline specific publication/document servers		
Architektur-Informatik	http://architektur-informatik.scix.net/cgi-bin/works/Home	Architektur-Informatik
CumInCAD Digital Archive	http://cumincad.architecturez.net/	CumInCAD Digital Archive
Elektronisch archivierte Theorie - Sammelpunkt	http://sammelpunkt.philo.at:8080/	Elektronisch archivierte Theorie - Sammelpunkt
Fluorophores.org	http://www.fluorophores.tugraz.at/	Fluorophores.org
PiezoMat.org	http://www.PiezoMat.org/	PiezoMat.org
RISC Publications	https://risc.jku.at/publications/	RISC Publications
Other		
Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation (fteval)	https://repository.fteval.at	Austrian Platform for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation (fteval)
European Research Papers Archive (ERPA)	http://eiop.or.at/erpa/	European Research Papers Archive (ERPA)

9 Recent publications

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